

Instruction Manual to set up the SITH-VR Experiment (Unreal Engine and VIVE Pro 2)

This is a step by step guide to start and run the HTC VIVE-VR version of the SITH experiment. I will explain the setup for the PC and the VR version. Especially when using VR mode, make sure to follow the order of the steps accurately since the VR connection can behave weirdly or not work entirely if the programs are not opened in the correct order. If there are any issues not addressed in this document feel free to contact me at my email address.

1. Move the PC to one side of your arena space and make sure it faces the arena. It should be positioned on the opposite side of where the starting position of the trials will be (Img. 1C).
2. Position the VR tracking devices on two corners of the room, not further than 7m apart. They should be mounted at 2m height minimum and facing slightly downwards towards the experimental area (Img. 1C). When plugged in a green light should be visible on both trackers (Img. 1A). The wireless tracker should be mounted on top of your monitor screen (Img. 1B), it does not light up when plugged in.

Image 1

- Turn on the PC and open the Unreal Engine (UE) Project file with **Unreal Engine 5.5.4!** The project is called **SITH_VR**. Also open the project folder in the file explorer. Make sure that in the "Saved" folder you can find another folder named "ExperimentData" and inside that a **Config.json** and **README.txt** file. Set up the configuration now following the instructions in README and make sure to save the Config.json document (Img. 2).

Image 2

- If you want to **play in PC mode** you can now start the game in UE by selecting **play in standalone game mode** (Img. 3). You can toggle Full-Screen Mode with F11. Make sure that a working audio device is connected to the PC and the sound card is turned on, if you are using it 😊.

The experiment is started by using the "Enter" key, a text block saying "Ready!" should pop up. You can move around using "WASD" and the mouse to look around. Each trial is started with "E" when standing on the starting position. You can confirm trials using "Space Bar". When the experiment is over you can quit the game by closing the window that opened when starting.

In case of sound issues, You can use the T-key to play a short sound sample and check if the sound is working; this works for PC and VR mode.

Image 3

5. If you want to **play in VR mode** you can now open the Vive Wireless and SteamVR programs (The unreal project always stays open during the next steps!) (Img. 4D). Connect the VR headset to a full battery via the USB cable at the back and turn it on by pressing the triangle button on the tracker in the back (Img. 4A), it should light up green and not be blinking. Also turn on the controllers by pressing and holding the buttons shown in the picture (Img. 4B). Make sure that all devices are being tracked by checking the SteamVR tracking menu (Img. 4D, bottom left, all symbols should be blue).

Image 4

6. Follow the **room setup** instructions for **standing only mode** (!) in the SteamVR menu (Img. 5B). When calibrating the room center stand in the middle of the SITH arena facing the PC, your back should be facing the experiment starting position (Img. 5A)! In VR you should be seeing the Steam VR home environment right now. Make sure you can see both your hands in VR.

Image 5

- You can now **start the game in VR**. The participant should be standing in the same position where the room center was calibrated facing the PC (Img. 5A). The experiment supervisor starts the game in **standalone game mode** (Img. 3). When starting it for the first time the loading can take a bit longer. The player should spawn in the middle of the room with the starting position behind them. If the room is shifted or rotated, disconnect and reconnect the VR headset and repeat the room setup.

The experiment also gets started by the supervisor using Enter. The participant can start trial using left trigger and confirm trials using right trigger (Img. 4C). “E” and “Space Bar” can also be used if necessary.

In case of sound issues, You can use the T-key to play a short sound sample and check if the sound is working; this works for PC and VR mode.

The data is saved after each trial so you can check that everything is working while the experiment is still ongoing. (A .json and .csv file should pop up after confirming each trial.)

- After the experiment is over you can quit the game by closing the separate window that shows the VR view on the PC. The data from your experiment gets saved in the same folder that the config is located in. Make sure to rename the experimentID variable before starting a new run. I also recommend moving the data files to a separate folder before starting a new experiment.

If your configuration is not working or data is not being saved, make sure that you didn't misspell any variables in the config and saved the document. (Correct spelling of all variables is shown in the example in README.) Make sure everything is located in the correct projects saved folder. The Config.json file must not be renamed!

If it still doesn't work, open the level blueprint of the UE project (Img. 6A). Go to the end of the variables list and make sure the SaveDirectory variable (Img. 6B) leads to the

ExperimentData folder of your project (Img. 6C). If the path is incorrect, copy the correct path in and replace all “\” characters with “/”. The string should end with .../ExperimentData/ (Img. 6C). Press compile and save in the top left corner (Img. 6D) and retry playing.

If the game doesn't open in VR, close the window that opened, check if you are playing in standalone game mode (Img. 3). The option “VR preview” in the play mode menu should be greyed out (Img. 3). If this is not the case, close all VR applications and the project file, reopen the project file first and then reconnect VR. You should not need to do the SteamVR room setup again.

If you cannot hear sound in VR, close all the VR software and the Unreal Project. Restart the PC. Reopen The Unreal Project first, then reconnect the VR setup. You should not need to do the room setup again.

If any problems remain, feel free to contact me.

Image 6

Image 6